

SOCIAL-LEGAL FACTORS OF IMPROVING THE ACTIVITY OF PUBLIC CONTROL INSTITUTIONS

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Developing the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, citizens' self-management bodies, trade unions, public associations, foundations, and mass media, which form the basis of civil society, i.e. civil society institutions and determine their content, democratization of our country in every way, increasing their role and importance, the fact that it is an important task to achieve the goal of implementing the principle of **"Towards a Strong Social Society"** is becoming the basis of all our reforms. Today, they are becoming an important factor in protecting democratic values, people's rights, freedom, and legal interests, creating conditions for citizens to realize their potential, social, and socio-economic activity, and legal culture. A developed structure of civil society should help to ensure inter-ethnic and inter-religious harmony, stability, and balance of interests in society, and support the effective functioning of the system of public control over the activities of state and administrative structures in our country. **Adoption of the newly revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan by popular vote in the referendum held on April 30, 2023, served** to strengthen the constitutional foundations of the establishment of New Uzbekistan.

The presidential election held by the newly revised Constitution once again shows the political maturity of our society and the full support of our people for the reforms being implemented to build a New Uzbekistan.

At the same time, the updated constitutional and legal conditions, it is required to improve the main directions of the country's development and bring the ongoing large-scale reforms to a new stage.

To realize the desire of our people to build a free prosperous and powerful **New Uzbekistan, to create all opportunities for every** citizen to develop their potential, to raise a healthy, educated, and morally perfect generation, to form a strong economy that has become an important link of global production, justice, law To guarantee priority, security, and stability, the adoption of Decree No. 158 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "**Uzbekistan-2030" strategy on September 11, 2023 can be considered** as one of the bright results of this.

Within the framework of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, it is aimed at achieving all the goals that have not lost their relevance, as well as ensuring the implementation of the tasks set in the New Uzbekistan development strategy. This decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, as well as the decision on measures to implement the "**Uzbekistan-2030" strategy in time and quality in 2023, are aimed at the consistent continuation** of the large-scale reforms and changes implemented in conditions of the new Uzbekistan, and the further development of sectors and directions.

Implementation of the new idea of "society is the initiator of reforms", expanding the scope of participation of the population in the management of state and community affairs, achieving the goals of the United Nations Organization for Sustainable Development, establishing close cooperation between citizens, society and the state, as well as public control over the activities of state bodies and institutions. to strengthen it, the Public Chamber was established under the **President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the public chambers** of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, and the city of Tashkent.

The Public Chamber was formed in the composition of 50 members working based on the public.

- The Public Chamber annually submits annual national reports to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the state of civil society and development trends;
- Participation of the members of the public chamber and regional public chambers in the open board meeting of each state body, as well as in the meetings of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the "Government hour", in the meetings of the Dzhokorgi Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, people's deputies of the regions and Tashkent city, district (city) councils have the right to do;
- The House of Commons and regional public houses have the right to send a request of the House of Commons to state bodies and organizations with the request to provide a reasoned explanation or state their opinion on the implementation of laws, state programs in various fields,

and other important issues within their competence. In this case, the state bodies and organizations must send the answer to the request no later than ten days from the date of its receipt, if no other deadline is set.

In Uzbekistan, complex organizational and legal measures are being implemented to strengthen the participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations, citizens' self-management bodies, and mass media in the implementation of public control and transparency in the activities of state authorities and management bodies.

- The purpose of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Control" is to regulate relations in the field of organization and implementation of public control over the activities of state bodies and institutions. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Control", the term "public control" refers to the provisions of the Constitution, laws, and other regulatory legal documents of state bodies and officials of the subjects of public control, as well as the political, socio-economic and cultural rights of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan. represents the activity of collecting, analyzing, and summarizing information on the unconditional implementation of international norms and principles. It is envisaged that the implementation of public control will be ensured based on principles such as the priority of protecting human rights and freedoms, voluntariness, legality, efficiency, transparency of public control, strict adherence to moral and ethical rules and norms in interactions with state bodies and officials. In the draft law, the implementation of regular public monitoring of the state of implementation of legislative norms on human rights, public sociological research and public hearings, reports on the activities of local state authorities on specific issues, as well as public examination of laws and other regulatory legal documents by civil society institutions, It is intended to create the necessary conditions for the participation of a person in making decisions related to his rights and interests.

- Preparation and holding of referendums, and elections, as well as implementation of public control in the field of defense, public safety and law and order, investigative activities, investigation, preliminary investigation, court proceedings, and execution of punishments are regulated by separate legal acts.

- As subjects of public control, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, self-government bodies of citizens, as well as non-governmental non-commercial organizations registered by the law, mass media operate.

- It is established that public control can be carried out by public councils, commissions, and other public organizational structures by the law.

- State bodies and their officials as objects of public control:
 - to take into account public interests and public opinion in the adopted normative legal documents, and decisions, as well as in state, sectoral, and regional development programs;
 - to ensure the implementation of the requirements of legal documents in the field of protecting the rights and legal interests of citizens, legal entities, and the interests of society;
 - to perform duties and functions assigned to him, related to social and public interests;
 - to provide public services;
 - activities related to the implementation of agreements, contracts, projects and programs implemented within the framework of social partnership are the object of public control.

To achieve the constitution and the rule of law, of course, effective use of the institution of public control is of great importance. This institution has existed in our country since ancient times in the form of the Council of Elders. These Councils were considered to be public structures engaged in neighborhood improvement, solving population problems, self-defense, always being alert, not neglecting children's upbringing, and other public works. Today, the factor of public control is very important in the effective functioning of state administration and authorities. The sphere of influence of this institute is extremely high in that the leaders and employees of state bodies strictly follow the laws and fulfill their duties and obligations responsibly.

Therefore, in the implementation of public control, first of all, it is necessary to further strengthen the role of all citizens, as well as non-governmental organizations and mass media. In this regard, a sense of responsibility, initiative, and involvement in the political, and socio-economic processes taking place in the country today should be formed in the mind of every person. If we are intolerant of any violations of the law, if we evaluate the actions of officials as a majority, and if we freely express our opinions, then the rule of law will be truly ensured.

Due to the results of pragmatic, open, and transparent new-stage reforms implemented in Uzbekistan in recent years, the sphere of influence of public control in our society has increased significantly. Everyone sees and knows that many shortcomings and problems, violations of the law are put an end to, especially in social networks, due to the attitude expressed towards the actions of state bodies and their leaders.

Public control serves balance, equality, mutual responsibility, and accountability in the relationship of the individual, society, and the state to achieve social justice. This institute ensures that human rights and freedoms are not only guaranteed by the state, but also have priority in the activities of state bodies, and the existence of public control is an indicator of the

fact that political power is literally in the hands of the people.

At this point, if we observe the role of public control in the activity of the courts, the practice of considering cases in mobile court sessions has been consistently established in Uzbekistan, which, in turn, serves to issue legal, justified, and fair judgments in the courts.

It is known that public participation in the fair consideration and legal resolution of criminal cases in courts is stipulated in the Constitution. According to it, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right to participate in the management of society and state affairs directly and through their representatives. The Law "On Courts" provides for the participation of people's advisers in the Criminal Court of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Regional Criminal Court, Tashkent City, District (City) Criminal Court, Military Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and Regional Military Courts.

Of course, the participation of people's councilors in courts is an important factor in ensuring the rule of law and social justice, as well as strengthening social relations between individuals, society, and the judiciary. At the same time, there is still work to be done to further ensure the transparency of the activities of judicial bodies, to expand open communication with the population, and especially to strengthen the role of the public in the administration of justice. In this regard, it will be useful to study the international practice and the experience of developed countries and apply the acceptable aspects to the judicial system of Uzbekistan.

In general, the goal of public control in the process of justice is to achieve fair and impartial court decisions regarding a specific court case. In short, the main tool of public control is the law. Public organizations monitor how state authorities and administrative bodies follow and enforce laws. The conclusions of the public control serve to critically review the activities of the executive power, correct errors, and ensure people's patriotism. The conclusion is that "state power" and "public control" are complementary concepts. The unity of state power and public control prevents the alienation of the people from the power, and the power from the people, and prevents the despotism of the minority and the majority. Ensuring the harmony of state power and public control serves the development of a democratic legal state and civil society.

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